

Semantic and linguacultural characteristics of color adjectives (using the example of English and Uzbek languages)

Halikova Shakhlo Uktamovna

TITLI, 10.00.06 – Comparative literature, comparative linguistics and translation studies, independent researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13269696>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 13-aprel 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 15-aprel 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 27-aprel 2024 yil

KEYWORDS

ABSTRACT

This article presents information on the study of color-related adjectives in modern English and their semantic, linguacultural characteristics on the example of the Uzbek and English languages.

Formation of a perfect system of training mature specialists in their field based on the newly acquired knowledge, rich intellectual heritage of mankind, modernization of the education system, achievements of science and culture, sports, economy, technique and technology are one of the important factors of the development of our country. Today, in the implementation of these goals, the deeply created conditions for young people and industry representatives in our country, the updating of the necessary resources for learning with world-class innovation and knowledge, and the attention to learning foreign languages are bearing their results[1, p. 172].

Knowledge of languages, including English, is becoming very important in establishing multilateral interstate relations, mutually beneficial trade-economic, technical and cultural relations between our country and developed countries. A qualified translator needs theoretical and practical knowledge, experience and cultural competence to receive information from the target language and transfer it to the mother tongue. At the same time, understanding the meaning of words and using them correctly is one of the main tasks of a linguist. The meaning of words and adjectives will be necessary assistants in this matter.

At this point, let us give information about the concept of lingua-cultural studies. Linguoculturology emerged at the intersection of linguistics, cultural studies, the study of the national culture's reflection and establishment in the language. The subject of science is the language and culture that interact [2, p.670]. Scientist V. N. Telia writes about it as follows: Linguistics is a science that studies the human, or rather, the cultural factor in a person. This means that the center of lingua-cultural studies is a complex of achievements characteristic of the anthropological paradigm of a person as a cultural phenomenon¹. According to G.G. Shishkin, linguoculturology is focused on the human factor, more precisely, on the cultural factor in a person. Linguistics is interconnected with the disciplines of linguistics, cultural studies, ethno psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, ethno linguistics, sociolinguistics. In particular, it is so closely connected with ethno linguistics and sociolinguistics that B. N. Telia considers it a form of ethno linguistics. However, they are fundamentally different disciplines. Semantics (Greek: semantikos - signifying, expressing) - the term was coined by the French linguist Michel Bréal (1832-1915), who is

considered the founder of modern semantics. , ran) the entire content, meaning, information expressed through; 2) department of linguistics, which studies the spiritual aspect of various language units; semasiology. Some lexical elements represent concepts, and these concepts can be represented only by complete sentences and their combinations. Consequently, the object of study of Semantics is basically the system of meanings of words and sentences with a complete, independent meaning. Semantics as a science began to develop in the second half of the 19th century and has passed through several qualitatively different stages [3, p. 172].

Human life cannot be imagined without colors. Color gloss, our life is beautiful and is of great importance in being content. Colors are very old.

It has been of social importance since time immemorial and it will give an opportunity to reflect to each nation unique lifestyle, customs and culture at a very high level. The impact of the diversity and mysteriousness of nature on the human psyche is the work of creators has been artistically researched by. Adjectives denoting color do not only denote color, each has its own semantics. It is distinguished by its structure and methodological features. Their style opportunities, the feature of expressing occasional themes occurs only in the speech process will come.

It is known that in Uzbek literature, writers and poets are examples of their creativity they make it colorful through colors. Because colors have a certain feeling, to the reader using sometimes open and sometimes symbolic glosses in expressing the experience. It is very important to make an impact, to bring it into that environment. An adjective represents a specific color. A specific color is, of course, reflected in something in nature. In such a case, if the color-denoting adjective is combined with word or phrase, which expresses something characteristic of the color, in the form of a determining compound, the meaning of the adjective is realized. That is, a determiner plays the role of a realizer. **Example:** *My pride is white cotton* (D. Hikmat). In this sentence, the adjective of white is given in the form of a clarifying compound with cotton wool. What is expressed in cotton is mostly white. In Uzbek linguistics, there is a long history of the study of words related to adjectives dates back to ancient times. By the 60s of the last century Uzbek linguist M. Sodikova made a great contribution in the study of words related to adjectives in linguistics. The scientist noted focusing on its semantics the largest group of sign words in science representing six different units, i.e. the words black, white, red, yellow, blue and green, which was analyzed on the basis of artistic text, (Sadikova, 1963, p. 8). [7, p. 15-16].

Color vocabulary is capable of clearly reflecting the way of life, history, and customs of a certain people. Perhaps, it is precisely because of such obvious national determinacy that it has always attracted the special attention of linguists. V. G. Kulpina asserts that "the concept of color linguistics as an independent scientific paradigm in modern linguistics is acquiring increasingly concrete features". Among the first to pay attention to this problem were the English anthropologists B. Berlin and P. Kay. [4, p. 283].

However, despite the fact that a considerable number of works have been devoted to the problem of studying color, the topic still retains its relevance, since it concerns the identification of linguacultural features of the semantics of color in the English language in a comparative aspect.

The color vision of the world of a particular nation is formed on the basis of its inherent values, traditions, customs and certain historical events. Accordingly, in any culture the concept of color is a historical, emotional and intellectual experience accumulated by a particular nationality. "Color is considered informative and a way to interpret and understand the meaning of designed environments". A study of the history of color designations in English showed that in the process of development of color vision, "the actualization of the components of the semantic structure of color names differed: some semes were dominant earlier, and some later, although all the main semes were initially included in the semantic volume of a color word, being clarified and differentiated ad

infinitem. Thus, it was not words that appeared, but meanings that were originally normalized by one meaning were actualized, and turned out to be significant". The English language contains several hundred names denoting the color palette [5, p.320]. At the same time, as was noted in the work of scientists L. V. Shubina and K. A. Dogadkina, the main ones are considered to be only white, black, green, red, yellow, blue, which form the main part of the "color micro fields of the secondary semantic plane", the total number of which in the English language is 32. On the other hand, this problem is considered by N. F. Alefirenko, who believes that the concept of color includes two components:

1. Basic image, i.e. the original meaning of a word that we can find in a dictionary. This image is formed as a result of subject-sensory thinking and, as a rule, is associated with a certain object of reality;
2. The layer of figurative meanings, or the cognitive layer, are those images that are formed as a result of developed abstract thinking and are associated with a certain context or have an idiomatic nature.

In other words, the direct nomination of color words is based on the process associations with certain realities the existence surrounding a person. "Color perception occurs when we connect our visual categories with specific, accessible to humans universal samples or models. So, to talk about color, we must project their perceptions onto what surrounds us". As for the secondary nomination, its origin, as a rule, is determined by the subjective factor, those associations that arise as a result of certain features of human thinking. Thus, we can once again emphasize the cultural determinacy of the figurative meanings of color adjectives in English.

Based on data obtained from various dictionaries, an analysis of basic and figurative concepts of adjectives-color designations was conducted. Let us turn to the analysis of the adjective white.

The Oxford Dictionary of English gives the following definition of the adjective white: **1.** Of the color of milk or fresh snow, due to the reflection of all visible rays of light; the opposite of black;

2. (Also White) belonging to or denoting a human group having light-colored skin (chiefly used of peoples of European extraction);

3. Counter-revolutionary or reactionary; Contrasted with red.

Oddly enough, white is considered one of the most controversial colors. On the one hand, at all times and among all people, its original meaning was "light", it was identified with life, purity, truth, nobility and beauty. On the other hand, it also has negative symbolism (evil, illness, suffering, death), which is explained by the fact that in many countries the color of the mourning clothes in which the deceased was dedicated to a new life was white. In English-speaking culture, the word-concept white confirms such symbolism [6, p.].

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